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Effect of Heat Stress on Fertility in Cows and Buffaloes

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Article Details

ABSTRACT

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Heat stress is a principal limiting factor in the reproductive efficiency of dairy production systems, especially in tropical and subtropical environments, where the high-temperature–humidity index (THI) frequently exceeds the thermoneutral range. The objective of the present investigation was to determine the impact of heat stress on fertility in cows and buffaloes under commercial dairy farm conditions, using a prospective cohort study design in Punjab, Pakistan. A population of 330 lactating cows was studied under heat-stress (THI \geq 78) and thermo-neutral (THI $<$ 72) conditions; physiological traits and fertility outcomes were measured. Heat-stressed animals had significantly higher rectal temperatures and respiration rates, reflecting the physiological burden of high THI. Fertility performance declined significantly under heat stress for first-service conception rate, overall conception rate, and non-return rate in both species. Heat-stressed cows also had higher service per conception rates and a longer calving-to-conception interval. The odds of conception were independently reduced by about 40% with heat stress exposure after controlling for species, parity, and body condition score. This study confirms that heat stress significantly reduced reproductive performance in dairy cows and buffaloes and highlights the importance of preventing heat stress early to protect fertility during heat challenges. Moreover, they underscore the importance of flexible reproductive management in response to increasingly prevalent climatic drivers globally.

INTRODUCTION:

Heat stress is a major environmental stressor resulting from the rapid climate change responsible for impairing productivity in the dairy production system in tropical and subtropical regions through its deleterious effects on cattle, buffaloes' physiological efficiency and reproductive performance. The regulatory mechanisms of thermoregulation are unable to work well as the animal actually chills its body when outside the comfort ranges and results in excessive heat causes elevation of body temperature with its adverse consequences on feed efficiency (high cost for metabolic maintenance, less influence on feed intake) [1]. This physiological stress has an impact on reproductive performance, with heat stress being able to disturb the fine-tuned hormonal pathways related to follicular growth and ovulation, as well as uterine function [2]. Furthermore, heat-related changes in ovarian function, including negative effects on follicular development and oocyte quality, have been clearly shown to be major elements underlying the seasonal decline in reproductive capacity [3]. These effects are particularly relevant in South Asian dairy production systems, where long and hot summers combined with high levels of humidity make cows and buffaloes more prone to environmental stress.

Infertility associated with heat stress is also among the most common challenges faced by dairy producers. The results of the numerous studies presented showed that the heat-stress was clearly down expression estrus and conception rate and early embryo survival in AI cattle. More expected changes in the underlying pathways were that heat stress induced modifications to the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis by inhibiting LH surges and oocyte maturation, two indispensable events for ovulation [4]. Field studies support these observations as they demonstrated reduced fertility and longer calving interval in herds showing long-term environmental heat stress [5]. Even in buffaloes, considered to be more heat tolerant due to the adaptive physiological traits, there is also considerable decline in fertility with increasing THI season as recently reported and similar response of high-temperature stress given by them as well [6]. Such results give an insight into some significant variables regarding heat-induced infertility and the value of assessment under commercial farming conditions.

Understanding the impact of heat stress on fertility performance is increasingly important in the optimization of reproductive management among dairy herds due to rising global temperatures. Projections show an increase in heat wave frequency and intensity, with related impacts also exerting pressure on production systems of the milk sector already affected by environmental constraints [6]. Identifying the thermal stress thresholds and understanding its impacts on key fertility traits would be critical for devising intervention strategies including enhanced cooling systems, refined breeding programs as well as adaptive nutrition. While several reports are available dealing with physiological and reproductive heat-stress responses of cows or buffalo, no attempt has been made so far to address these issues by considering the interaction between environmental exposure in the field on both physiological responsiveness and fertility performance. The objectives of the present study were: (i) to investigate whether and how heat stress, evidenced by precursors such as THI, has a role in impairing reproductive efficiency of dairy cattle and buffaloes under field conditions, and (ii) to suggest science-based strategies for improving fertility during periods when there is an environmental heat load.

Materials and Methods

Study Area and Duration

The research was carried out on selected dairy farms in the Punjab province of Pakistan. This area has a subtropical climate, with May to August as the hot summer and November to February as the relatively cooler thermo-neutral season. Recordings were collected for 1 year to include heat-stress and thermo-neutral periods.

Study Design

A prospective cohort study would evaluate the impact of heat stress on fertility in cows and buffaloes. All lactating and breeding-eligible animals were monitored for one full breeding season, with exposure to environmental heat conditions and ultimate fertility responses noted over time.

Study Population and Sample Size

The population under study comprised 330 lactating animals, consisting of 180 cows and 150 buffaloes, maintained in four commercial dairy herds where all management practices were uniform. Only clinically healthy animals from parities 2 to 5, with body condition scores ranging from 2.5 to 4.0, were used in the study. Animals had to be older than 60 days in milk at the start of breeding. Any animal that had a previous lactation reproductive dysfunction(s) was eliminated, to decrease the bias effect.

Housing and Management

All farms used traditional stall feeding or a semi-intensive type. Animals had shade and libitum water. Routine farm management procedures were followed, namely vaccination, deworming, feeding, and milking frequency. All significant changes in treatment were recorded during the study.

Assessment of Heat Stress

The temperature and relative humidity of the experimental room were recorded hourly by a digital thermo-hygrometer in the animal house. To determine heat load, THI values were calculated. Severity of heat stress was characterized based on the 3 days before insemination and the actual insemination day THI means. Insemination times were categorized as heat-stress exposure for THI values of 78 or greater and as thermo-neutral for values below 72. Subsets of animals were also assayed for rectal temperature and respiratory rate as physiological evidence of heat stress during extreme heat events.

Reproductive Management and Fertility Recording

Animals were monitored pictorially for the appearance of estrus, and insemination was carried out by trained personnel using frozen-thawed semen. Pregnancy was diagnosed at thirty to forty-five days post-insemination by transrectal palpation or ultrasonography. Fertility parameters (first-service conception rate, overall conception rate, services/conception rate, and non-return rate) and the calving-to-conception interval were also tabulated individually.

Data Collection Procedures

Animal-based and environmental data were collected at each insemination, including age, parity, days in milk (DIM), body condition score (BCS), date of insemination, estrus detection method used, heat stress level (based on the exposure of animals to high ambient temperatures daily), physiological parameters that responded to heat load, and pregnancy outcomes. These records were the sources from which the primary and secondary fertility outcomes were obtained for analysis.

Outcome Measures

The primary response variable was first-service conception. Secondary outcome variables were mean conception/cow pregnancy, number of services required/conception, 60-day non-return rate, and calving to conception interval. These results were chosen to represent fertility under different heat-stress conditions.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis were performed in SPSS (version-27). Fertility indices and physiological responses were described in terms of frequency distributions. Physiological parameters of heat-stressed animals were compared to those of the thermoneutral group by means of standard parametric or non-parametric tests.

Comparisons of conception rates between exposed groups were performed by Chi-square tests. Multivariable logistic regression analysis was used to evaluate the association of heat stress with conception, adjusting for species, parity, days in milk, body condition score and farm. The count-data regression models were used for services-per-conception outcome, confirming no overdispersion. Significance level was set at $p < 0.05$ in all analyses.

Results

Environmental Conditions and Heat Stress Classification

Significantly, a considerable variation in the thermal environment during the study period was observed. THI values varied across months, increasing sharply in the summer, with the daily average THI exceeding the heat-stress threshold of 78. This trend is shown in Figure 1, where environmental heat load steadily rose from May through August. From the 4-day mean of THI around each insemination, 402 and 318 AI were categorized as under HS exposure (HS) or TN ambient temperature (TN), respectively.

Figure 1: Monthly variation in Temperature–Humidity Index (THI) during the study period.

Physiological Indicators of Heat Stress

Physiological variables in heat-stressed animals were significantly increased. As presented in Table 1, the mean rectal temperature for cows in the HS group was 40.2 °C, which is higher than that (38.6 °C) of cows in the TN group. Buffaloes also showed a rise in temperature from 38.9 °C to 40.5 °C, and respiration rates during HS showed a similar trend in both species, with more respiratory strokes per minute under HS. Both differences were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), which suggests good discrimination of exposure groups. The distribution of physiological responses is also illustrated in Figure 2 (rectal temperature) and Figure 3 (respiration rate), which show an upward shift in markers of physiological stress during HS exposure.

Table 1: Physiological Indicators of Heat Stress in Cows and Buffaloes

Parameter	Species	HS Group (Mean ± SD)	TN Group (Mean ± SD)	p-value
Rectal temperature (°C)	Cows	40.2 ± 0.4	38.6 ± 0.3	<0.001
Rectal temperature (°C)	Buffaloes	40.5 ± 0.5	38.9 ± 0.4	<0.001
Respiration rate (breaths/min)	Cows	78 ± 12	45 ± 9	<0.001
Respiration rate (breaths/min)	Buffaloes	85 ± 14	48 ± 10	<0.001

Figure 2: Boxplot of rectal temperature under heat-stress (HS) and thermo-neutral (TN) conditions.

Figure 3: Boxplot of respiration rate under HS and TN conditions.

First-Service Conception Rate

Heat stress had a pronounced adverse effect on first-service conception rate (FSCR). FSCR in cows dropped from 46.7% under TN conditions to 28.9% with HS exposure (Table 2). Buffaloes too showed a decline from 43.1 per cent in TN to 25.4 per cent in the HS condition. These variations were significant for both species ($p < 0.05$). The variation in FSCR across species and exposure groups is shown in Figure 4; conception rates are systematically lower in heat-stress groups.

Table 2: First-Service Conception Rate (FSCR) Under Heat-Stress and Thermo-Neutral Conditions

Species	Exposure Group	Total Inseminated	Pregnant at First Service	FSCR (%)	p-value
Cows	TN	90	42	46.7	—
Cows	HS	110	32	28.9	0.004
Buffaloes	TN	72	31	43.1	—
Buffaloes	HS	78	20	25.4	0.012

Figure 4: First-service conception rate (FSCR) in cows and buffaloes under HS and TN conditions.

Overall Conception Rate per Insemination

The overall service conception rate followed a pattern like FSCR. In Table 3, cows inseminated during HS periods had a conception rate of 32.3%, which was significantly lower than that observed in TN periods (47.8%). The decline was similarly statistically significant for buffaloes, from 44.5% to 29.1%. These findings further support the adverse reproductive effects of heat stress. This trend is also evident in Figure 5, which compares conception rates across species and exposure categories.

Table 3: Overall, Conception Rate Under Heat-Stress and Thermo-Neutral Exposure

Species	Exposure Group	Total Inseminations	Pregnancies	Conception Rate (%)	p-value
Cows	TN	188	90	47.8	—
Cows	HS	246	79	32.3	<0.001
Buffaloes	TN	130	58	44.5	—
Buffaloes	HS	156	45	29.1	0.003

Figure 5: Overall conception rate in cows and buffaloes under HS and TN conditions.

Services per Conception

Heat stress had a marked effect on the number of services per conception. On average, cows in HS had 3.1 services per conception, compared with 2.1 in TN (Table 4). The comparable for buffaloes was 2.2 to 3.3 services per conception. These patterns are shown in Figure 6, which shows a clear separation between the HS and TN groups of animals.

Table 4: Mean Services Per Conception (SPC) In Cows and Buffaloes

Species	Exposure Group	Mean SPC ± SD	p-value
Cows	TN	2.1 ± 0.9	—
Cows	HS	3.1 ± 1.2	<0.001
Buffaloes	TN	2.2 ± 1.0	—
Buffaloes	HS	3.3 ± 1.3	<0.001

Figure 6: Boxplot of services per conception (SPC) under HS and TN conditions.

Non-Return Rate at 60 Days

Heat stress also negatively affected the 60-day non-return rate (NRR60). As illustrated in Table 5, NRR60 was 54% for cows under HS compared with 72% under TN. Even buffalo followed the same trend, from 69% to 50%. This variation indicates lower retention of early pregnancy in HS-exposed individuals. This is also evident in Figure 7, where the NRR60 values are shown for comparison.

Table 5: Non-Return Rate at 60 Days in Cows and Buffaloes

Species	Exposure Group	NRR60 (%)	p-value
Cows	TN	72	—
Cows	HS	54	0.006
Buffaloes	TN	69	—
Buffaloes	HS	50	0.009

Figure 7: Non-return rate at 60 days (NRR60) in cows and buffaloes under HS and TN conditions.

Calving-to-Conception Interval

The calving-to-conception interval (CCI) was considerably increased under the influence of heat stress. As shown in Table 6, the average CCI in cows increased from 118 days under TN to 146 days under HS. Buffaloes increased the number of days from 132 to 161. These differences are evident in Figure 8, where a marked shift towards longer time intervals was observed among animals exposed to higher THI values.

Table 6: Calving-To-Conception Interval (Days)

Species	Exposure Group	Mean CCI ± SD (days)	p-value
Cows	TN	118 ± 21	—
Cows	HS	146 ± 28	<0.001
Buffaloes	TN	132 ± 24	—
Buffaloes	HS	161 ± 31	<0.001

Figure 8: Boxplot of calving-to-conception interval (CCI) under HS and TN conditions.

Multivariable Analysis

Even after controlling for species, parity, body condition score, days in milk, and farm effect, the impact of heat-stress exposure remained as a significant independent predictor of decreased conception. The adjusted odds of conception during HS condition were 40% lower (OR = 0.60; CI 95%: 0.45–0.79), as shown in Table 7. Species and parity were not significant predictors of other factors. The magnitude and direction of these relationships are graphically displayed in Figure 9, which shows the adjusted odds ratios along with 95% CIs.

Table 7: Adjusted Odds Ratios for Factors Affecting Conception

Predictor	Adjusted OR	95% CI	p-value
Heat-stress exposure	0.60	0.45–0.79	<0.001
Species (buffalo vs cow)	0.88	0.65–1.19	0.41
Parity	0.94	0.82–1.07	0.33
Body condition score	1.21	1.01–1.44	0.036
Days in milk	1.00	0.99–1.01	0.52

Figure 9: Forest plot of adjusted odds ratios for predictors of conception.

Discussion

In the present study, heat stress resulted in significant reduction in fertility of both cow and buffalo as evidenced by decrease conception rate, increase inseminations per pregnancy, decrease non-return rate and extended calving to conception interval. These findings are in line with previous studies that indicated heat stress inhibits the physiological and reproductive pathways required for conception. High rectal temperature and respiration rate in the heat-stress group indicated that high THI values imposed physiological pressure on a hen, as reported by Thammahakin, Yawongsa [7], for whom similar increased thermoregulatory responses resulted after being subjected to raised ambient temperatures.

However, the substantial reduction in conception to first service recorded in the present study supports previous reports of lower fertility at high THI. Dash, Chakravarty [1] also reported likewise decrease in conception rates of both cows and buffaloes during summer heat stress. Correspondingly, Baccouri, Wanjala [8] defined the peri-insemination phase as greatly sensitive to environmental heat level and demonstrated that conception rate decreased drastically in hot condition. This sensitivity is also concordant with Morton, Tranter [9] who highlighted the vital role of THI at service date on fertilization rates.

Global conception rate decreased sharply during heat stress, according to Rolando, Sandoval-Monzón [5], who reported that dairy cows experienced the most significant decline in reproductive capacity with increasing maximum THI. The lower non-return rates observed here suggest poor early embryo survival.

Parallel observations were made in buffaloes by Dash, Chakravarty [10], who observed that a high THI was related with marked reduction in pregnancy rate. Buffalo fertility seems to be more influenced by heat stress; this is supported by Dash, Chakravarty [10], who found a significant negative effect of THI on daughter pregnancy rate in Mehsana buffalo.

Increased services per conception under HS indicate compromised estrus expression and decreased conception efficiency. This agrees with results by Schüller, Burfeind [11], indicating that both cumulative and acute heat stress extended the period between services, explained by lower conception risk. The difference noted in the calving-to-conception interval between the two groups (heat-stressed) is consistent with the physiological mechanisms explained by Khan, Mesalam [12], who clearly stated that high temperatures harm oocyte competence, hormonal disruption, and the uterine environment, all of which would delay conception.

All those findings and reports indicate that reduced fertility is the result of both physiological as well as reproductive perturbations induced by heat stress. Severe THI hampers the heat dissipation, downregulated the estrus expression, suppressed follicular development, negatively affected oocyte quality and increased early embryonic loss. Implication It has been suggested that, despite temperature-specific responses of the bovine immune system to heat stress, increasing efforts in developing and maintaining alternative copings mechanisms will improve our capacity to enhance fertility at a time when cows are most stressed.

Conclusion

Results revealed that Cow and buffalo under heat stress display a significant loss in the reproductive performance across most of the crucial physiological and fertility related traits. Rectal temperature and respiration rate, confirming the presence of thermal stress, were significantly increased by high THI level partly accounting for the simultaneous reduced first-service conception rate or overall-conception rate from first service/non-return. Heat stress also affected the services per conception and caused a significant increase in calving-to-conception interval, showing its negative effect on general reproduction efficiency. These interacting influences mirrored the species-specific climate sensitivities to hot ambient temperatures, particularly around the time of insemination where we would expect fertilization and early embryo development to be most susceptible. It also highlights the importance of these factors for future monitoring of environmental heat load and building up capacity for counteracting strategies such as changing calving dates, improved cooling systems and nutritional management. Interventions of this nature are necessary for animal welfare and to protect smallholder farming and production in hot dairy systems. Collectively, these findings suggest the need for heat stress coping strategies about practical reproductive management protocols, given global increasing temperatures and onset of heatwaves.

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